

Character Education Strategies of Eating in Indonesian Schools

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ABSTRACT: Character education is an effort to develop characters so that the desired character values can be achieved. Character education strategies of eating are important and strategic to ensure a balanced, halal, thoyib, and civilized nutritional intake. Therefore, this study aimed at examining the character education strategies of eating in Indonesian schools. The method of study used Systematic Review. The data sources of this study were in the form of journal articles and relevant sources both online and even offline, in which it was related to eating character education. Data analysis methods used in this study were meta-analysis for quantitative data and meta-synthesis for qualitative data. Based on the study results, it can be concluded that there are 6-character education strategies of eating in Indonesian schools, namely: reinforcement of daily meal policy, reinforcement of eating manners, learning of halal and thoyib food, reinforcement of healthy eating habits, reinforcement of healthy canteens and nutrition programs, and reinforcement of outdoor class activities. Those six-character education strategies of eating are mostly done by full-day schools, featured schools, favorite schools, and model schools at both the primary and secondary education levels in Indonesia.

Keywords-Strategies, Character, Eating, School, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Character education is an effort to develop the character so that the desired character values can be achieved. Character education is carried out by means of knowledge components, awareness, willingness, and action to carry out the character values instilled. Character education is enforced in each level of education, starting from primary education to higher education. Character education is more emphasized in primary education since it will be difficult to change someone's character if character is not formed early. Character education has been a part of public schools in the United States since its inception. This character education has undergone dramatic changes over the years, from didactic instruction to service-learning. The character education program has a positive impact on the students' behavior. Character education has to be an integral part from the curriculum, it is not taught as a separate subject. This includes not only academic subjects but also specialized fields i.e. art, music, and physical education. Class rules should be based on good character principles, and the teachers have to create a good character model to be observed by the students. Additionally, the students must be taught with the character through direct service activities that give a contribution to the school, community, and public society [1].

The implementation of character education through a full-day school concept in Kota Semarang has been implemented. There is a positive effect of implementing a full-day school in schools with the growth and development of student character [2]. The character education through lesson plans will have an impact on the students' behavior when the students are not under the supervision of the classroom teacher. Positive changes occur in the students' behavior who follow the character learning [3].

The strategies of character education can be in the form of Character Building where the activities are established to improve the emotional intelligence of students, Caring School Communities where these activities are organized to create a caring relationship between teacher and students, and Integrative Ethics Education model which has five steps for moral character development (supportive climate, ethical skills, instruction of internship, self-regulation, and adopting a systems development approach). Moreover, the teachers should have Professional Religiosity with four basic principles in teaching in the classroom such as Amanah, Rahmah, Taadubah and Sillah [4].

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Character education also can use technologies. Technology devices create an integration of these foundations that is feasible, and technology offering is a new way to positively contribute to the character education. Since the education system is heavily influenced by new technologies, structural changes have to be carried out to teach process skills as well as content knowledge to meet the needs of all children [5]. The character education strategies of eating are very important and strategic to ensure a balanced, halal, thoyib, and civilized nutritional intake for the children. Based on this background, this study aims to examine the character education strategies of eating in Indonesian schools.

METHOD

The method of this study used was a systematic review. According to [6] and [7], a Systematic review aims to conduct an identification, evaluation, and interpretation towards the whole results of the study and relevant sources related for a certain topic. Data sources of this study were journal articles and relevant sources both online and even offline, in which it was related to eating character education. The relevant sources were school sites which became the object of study and relevant overseas institutions. Perry [8] postulated that the procedures of Systematic Review covered up: 1) identification of research problems, 2) research protocol development, 3) determining the location of the research results database, 4) selection of relevant research results, 5) selection of quality research results, 6) data extraction, and 7) presentation of the results. The data analysis method used in this study covered up meta-analysis for quantitative data and meta-synthesis for the qualitative data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There were 6-character education strategies of eating, namely: reinforcement of daily meal policy, reinforcement of eating manners, learning of halal and thoyib food, reinforcement of healthy eating habits, reinforcement of healthy canteens and nutrition programs, and reinforcement of outdoor class activities. Those six-character education strategies of eating were mostly done in the full-day schools, superior schools, favorite schools, and model schools both in the primary and even secondary level of education in Indonesia.

Reinforcement of Daily Meal Policy

An important supporting factor in the implementation of the daily meal policy is character education through daily meals [9]. The success of the nutrition education policy implementation program at SDIT Insan Permata of Malang could be seen from the character and tradition of eating a balanced, healthy, diverse, and Islamic diet that was getting stronger. A dominant factor that was important and strategic in the implementation of nutrition education policy at SDIT Insan Permata of Malang was the desire of the parents of students that their children had a tradition of eating a balanced and healthy diet. The implementation of nutrition education policy at SDIT Insan Permata of Malang had an individual impact (on the students) and social impacts (on the parents) with the better the tradition of eating of students both at school, at home, and in the environment [10].

Reinforcement of Eating Manners

The learning level of the applicative moral values of students' eating manners was in the high category. The results level of the lunch program at SDIT Bina Anak Sholeh Giwangan Yogyakarta, were quite effective in cultivating the children's character values [11].

Education of religious character and discipline in primary school-age children has been proven to be quite good with the role and functions of school principals and teachers which are very vital or important with the assistance of all school members. The school's efforts are to maintain and improve the habit of eating, drinking, and praying first and not standing up [12].

The students' character developments are not only in the learning but also in the habituation, mentoring, as well as the culture that has been attached to the school. The etiquette of manners in the mosque, the manners of eating, politeness, the manners of prayer, the manners of talking with others are included in the hidden curriculum [4].

SD Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 02 of Purwokerto implemented the lunch activity in school. Uniquely, this activity was emphasized not just the fulfillment of balanced nutrition, but also the formation of positive characters for the children. Additionally, through the habituation of having lunch together, it was expected that it could cause to emerge a sense of empathy for the students. The teachers always required students to pray before eating. With maximum supervision, the students prayed fervently before eating. This fostered gratitude for the character of the students. The sense of togetherness could be seen clearly when the students did not overtake each other when eating. The next character that was built was a sense of responsibility shown by the activity of cleaning up the food scraps and putting the plates and spoons back into the basket that had been provided. In addition to eating etiquette, it was also emphasized some good characters through lunch activities at school. Some of them were the culture of queuing, being grateful, appreciating and responsible.

At SMPN 17 of Bekasi, Joint lunch activities were often carried out to learn the meal etiquette, creating togetherness, and increasing brotherhood among the students. Those activities were quite successful, the students were very happy to have lunch together with friends and teachers. After the congregational Zuhur prayer at the school mosque, they immediately sat neatly in their chairs. After praying which was led by the class president, they orderly finished their food. To get rid of boredom, there were

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students' styles of enjoying their lunch. There were students who continued to sit in their chairs, some were on the floor, some were in groups, some were under the tree in front of the classroom and some were sitting on the garden chairs. All this brought its own enjoyment to the students. Thus, they are still enthusiastic to follow the lessons in the next half until evening.

LEARNING OF HALAL AND THOYIB FOOD

Indonesia, as the most populous Muslim country, has decided Islamic Religious Education as a compulsory subject to be taught in the curriculum at all levels of education from primary schools to secondary schools. "Halal and thoyib" food is one of the topics to be discussed in the Islamic Religious Education curriculum. The holy book of Al-Qur'an reminds all Muslims of the words "halalan thayyiban". The word "thayyib" means good, referring to good qualities and healthy values. "Halalan Thayyiban" means it is permitted according to Islamic law and it is also of good quality and health. Most of the students agreed that they were used to eating and drinking healthy and nutritious food. They felt strongly against, sometimes even, eating expensive food, even though it was "haram" (forbidden) and not good for our health. At the same time, most of them denied that eating "haram" foods could actually make our bodies healthy and strong. In the case of the "halal" label on market products, the sample of students paid less attention to the "halal" label before deciding to buy a product [13].

Reinforcement of Healthy Eating Habits

Direct approaches such as gardening and cooking programs could encourage greater consumption of vegetables and might have greater effect than nutrition education. Providing the students with free, accessible fruit and vegetables has been experimentally shown to have a positive impact on long-term eating behavior [14].

The students' behavior during the school lunch program in the aspect of the responsibility value was in the very high category, the aspect of caring value was in the medium category, the aspect of discipline value was in the high category, the aspect of honesty value was in the high category, and the aspect of persistence value that grew up in the students was very high [11].

Reinforcement of Healthy Canteens and Nutrition Programs

The Ministry of Education and Culture built 315 healthy canteens in pilot schools throughout Indonesia. The Ministry of Education and Culture's Director of Primary School Development said that the healthy canteen program was also land for character education. Character education in the canteen must be carried out, how to eat in the right culture, queue culture, then how food should be healthy, wash clean hands, pray before eating, eat with the right hand, how to place dirty dishes and teach the students to wash alone.

At SD Negeri 3 Panderejo of Banyuwangi, the school canteen was not just a place to stop to eat and a place for buying and selling food, but a place to build character. In the school canteen, there was habituation which ensured the character that could be built up in this place. The students got a similar right in shopping. They had to get into the habit of holding back in line to wash their hands. When they went to the food display room, they needed to use their intelligence to select and buy the food according to their tastes and needs. The students also needed to adjust the contents of their pockets when transacting. After leaving the display room, the students enjoyed the food by choosing a place they like, but still wanted to share a bench with other friends. The food display made from local food could foster a love of the country, preserve the nation's culture, and develop the economy of the community around the school. The ritual of eating also needed to be monitored. Memorizing prayers before eating needed to be implemented and gave thanks for the sustenance of the moment. When eating, did not make a sound and the students must finish the food they bought. The students were encouraged to share food with their friends. Habitual responsibility was continued by washing cutlery and washing hands. It was ended by removing the waste separately between organic and inorganic.

At SDN 1 Kauman of Malang city, the existence of a healthy canteen was one of student entrepreneurship activities, where the students sold various processed products from fried rice (nasi goreng), nasi uduk, nasi kuning, spaghetti, burgers, pancakes, healthy soup, pudding, various drinks, and other snacks that were halal and thoyib.

On November 4th, 2019, The Ministry of Education and Culture had been working with Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Regional Centre for Food and Nutrition (SEAMEO RECFON) to give Nutrition Program Award for Achievement (Nutrition Goes to School/NGTS) to nine schools in Indonesia. The NGTS Awards 2019 were given to the primary, junior high school and senior high school and also vocational high school levels throughout Indonesia. There were 253 teachers of 84 schools in the primary to Senior High School/Vocational High School levels and equivalent from 27 districts in 12 provinces in Indonesia who had participated in presenting the Nutrition for Achievement Program activities that had been implemented in their respective schools. The entire team was then selected to become 30 finalists who were invited to Jakarta to present their ideas and programs in front of the jury. The list of winners of the 2019 NGTS Awards for the primary school Category was: 1st place from SD Negeri 1 of Motoboi Kecil Sulawesi Utara, 2nd place from SD Negeri of Gunung Sitoli Sumatera Utara, and 3rd place from SD Negeri Mejayan 01 of Jawa Timur. For the category of Junior High School-Senior High School was: 1st place from SMP Negeri 1 of Sidoharjo Jawa Tengah, 2nd place from SMA Negeri 1 of Pati Jawa Tengah, and the 3rd place from SMP Negeri 7 of Bojonegoro Jawa Timur. For the category of vocational High School was: the 1st place from SMK Tunas Harapan of Pati Jawa Tengah, 2nd place from SMK Wikrama of Bogor Jawa Barat, and the 3rd place from SMK Negeri 5 of Banjarmasin Kalimantan Selatan.

Reinforcement of Outdoor Class Activities

At SD Muhammadiyah 9 of Malang city, the outdoor class activities which were packaged with a store tour model, shopping experience, and eating fruit together turned out to be more effective in providing education about the importance of healthy food.

At SD Muhammadiyah 4 of Malang city, the outdoor class activities were by visiting the Integrated Laboratory of the Faculty of Agriculture and Animal Husbandry, University of Muhammadiyah Malang. During this visit, the students of 1st grade of SD Muhammadiyah 4 of Malang city were taught a lot about the importance of consuming vegetables and fruits at an early age. In addition, dozens of students were also introduced to many names of vegetables and their benefits, and were taught how to grow vegetables.

CONCLUSION

Departing from the results of the study, it can be concluded that: 1) there are 6- character education strategies of eating in Indonesian schools, namely: reinforcement of daily meal policy, reinforcement of eating manners, learning of halal and thoyib food, reinforcement of healthy eating habits, reinforcement of healthy canteens and nutrition programs, and reinforcement of outdoor class activities, 2) Those six character education strategies of eating are mostly done by full-day schools, featured schools, favorite schools, and model school both in the primary and secondary school levels in Indonesia.

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